

PECULIARITIES OF VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the basics of non-verbal communication: its definition, functions and structure. The problem of continuity of transmission of non-verbal messages of communicants is analyzed. The differences between verbal and non-verbal communication are indicated. The validity of the question that non-verbal messages more accurately convey the true intentions of communicants has been proved.

Key words: non-verbal communication, learning, language, gestures, communication, process.

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Learning a foreign language is not just about learning vocabulary and grammar. A foreign language is a culture, and non-verbal communication as part of the culture of the country in which the language is being learned should be taught and learned in the classroom. The language of nonverbal communication is not universal. It has national characteristics that must be taken into account when communicating with foreigners. Ignorance of this feature can create significant obstacles to successful communication.

In addition, nonverbalism can be very effective in the learning process itself. This is explained by the fact that the situational nature of the perception of the environment, characteristic of children, attracts attention primarily to facial expressions and gestures, and when reproduced in the child's mind, all links in the chain are interconnected.

The purpose of this article is to prove that nonverbal language can be not only a subject of study, but also a successful tool in teaching a foreign language. As Makarenko wrote, for him "like for many experienced teachers, such "little things" became decisive: how to stand, how to sit, how to raise your voice, smile, how to look" [1].

In the interaction between teacher and children, nonverbal communication occurs through several channels:

- Facial expressions;
- touch;
- Gestures;
- Communication distance;
- visual interaction;
- Intonation.

American scholar Albert Mehrabian notes that frequent use of gestures is accompanied by a more collaborative teaching style that encourages compassion and cooperation. It also analyzes how a teacher's facial expression (such as a smile) attracts more attention and encourages students to respond more often than words. It has been found that the more a

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teacher uses the blackboard, the less effective teaching will be due to the lack of non-verbal communication, the lack of interaction.

Some scientists argue that teacher nonverbal behavior (close communication, smiling, eye contact, gestures) is very effective in attracting students to the teacher. It was also clarified that students are more engaged and feel connected to the teacher, for example, when the teacher stands in the aisle or moves down the aisle. When the teacher is seated, interaction between him and the class is greatly limited. It is important that the teacher pays non-verbal attention not only to the first desks, but also establishes contact with each student.

A special place in the teacher's nonverbal communication system is occupied by the system of gestures. The teacher's gestures are for students one of the indicators of his attitude towards them. Grant and Henning note that 82% of teacher communication is through gestures, especially expressions of feelings. The nature of the teacher's gestures creates a certain mood in the class from the first minutes. If the teacher's movements are nervous, tension arises in the classroom. Gestures also play an important role in attracting students' attention as the emotional richness of a gesture attracts the attention of the audience. Among the means of organizing attention, almost every teacher actively uses gestures such as pointing, imitating and emphasizing gestures. With the help of a gesture, the teacher establishes mandatory feedback with the student (questioning nod of the head, inviting gestures, etc.), increases its intensity (gestures of approval, evaluation) or terminates contact.

Tone of voice also matters a lot when communicating between teacher and student. When communicating between adults, intonation can account for up to 40% of the information. When communicating with a child, the effect of intonation intensifies. Intonation reveals the attitude that accompanies the teacher's speech. The child surprisingly accurately recognizes the attitude of adults towards him; he has an exceptional "emotional ear". The teacher's shout or monotonous speech loses its power because the student's sensory impressions are either blocked by the shout, or he does not perceive the emotional accompaniment at all, which leads to indifference. The teacher's speech should be emotionally rich, and extremes should be avoided. In a foreign language, simply tapping the rhythm helps students develop the correct intonation and find the features of the intonation pattern. All the teacher has to do is set the rhythm of the sentence and the student has to read the sentence with the correct stress.

The above findings indicate that nonverbal communication plays an indispensable role in creating a learning environment conducive to successful learning. Teachers must be proficient in nonverbal language because children "read" the teacher's behavior, mood and attitude. Therefore, teachers should become more aware of the role that nonverbal communication plays in teaching and strive to transform the unconscious use of gestures into conscious use to make teaching more effective.

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